

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D4.1 Design of the future OA Publishing Capacity Centre

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ	PL

	AKADEMII NAUK	
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AJOL	African Journals Online
ALMASI	Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally
ANR	Agence Nationale de la Recherche
AUP	Acceptable Use Policy
BPA	Blueprint Architecture
CMDB	Configuration Management Database
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
FitSM	Federated IT Service Management
FSD	Funders, Sponsors, Donors

IdP	Identity Provider
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Technology Provider
LS	Learned Society
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OA	Open Access
OADJS	OA Diamond Journals Study
OIDC	OpenID Connect
ORE	Open Research Europe
OS	Open Science
RAA	Research Assessment Agency
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
TF	Task Force
WAYF	Where are you from

Executive Summary

This report presents the design and development of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), a federated infrastructure that supports Diamond Open Access publishing in the European Research Area.

The EDCH was officially launched in January 2025 and builds upon the foundations laid by the EU funded DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects. Its mission is to offer services and resources to Diamond Open Access Publishers, Service and Technology Providers, as well as foster their collaboration at both national and European levels.

The report underscores the role of the EDCH as a response to the fragmentation of the Diamond OA landscape and presents its main services to key stakeholders. Additionally, it outlines the governance of the EDCH as a coordinated infrastructure, and its operational model that fosters community engagement and is implemented via dedicated Task Forces.

1. Introduction

This report¹ is an output of the DIAMAS Task 4.1 “Building a Common Access Point for IPSP”, which focuses on the design of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), and the establishment of a governance and technical framework that will support its operation in the long term. The report describes the conceptual design of the EDCH and presents its structural components and services to the Diamond Open Access (OA) community in Europe; it also outlines the plan for its further development as a federated infrastructure that aims to support an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable OA scholarly communication ecosystem.

Background

Commissioned by cOAlition S and funded by Science Europe, the *Open Access Diamond Journals Study*² (OADJS, Bosman et al. 2021) explored “collaborative non-commercial OA publishing models for OA (a.k.a Diamond OA)”, providing an analysis of the global landscape of Diamond OA journals and platforms. The most important finding of the study was that nonprofit OA publishing worldwide can be characterised as a largely fragmented archipelago of 17.000 to 29.000 journals. The most important recommendation of OADJS was to establish a dedicated Capacity Centre for Diamond OA that would align, coordinate, and improve the sustainability of nonprofit Diamond OA publishing.

This study gave rise to the *Action Plan for Diamond OA in 2022*,³ an initiative of Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency (ANR) to further develop and expand a sustainable, community-driven Diamond OA scholarly communication ecosystem. The Action Plan proposed to align and develop common resources for the entire Diamond OA community, including journals and platforms, while respecting the cultural, multilingual, and disciplinary diversity that constitutes its strength. These actions contributed to an increasing recognition of Diamond OA as an alternative to publishing models that are inherently inequitable and increasingly unsustainable. Political support for Diamond OA came with the UNESCO *Recommendation on Open Science* (2021), the G7 Science and Technology Ministers

¹ The report is also available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15433072>

² Bosman, Jeroen, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, & Proudman, Vanessa. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1:

Findings. <https://zenodo.org/record/4558704#.YPmY1S1w1MJ> (OPERAS, SPARC Europe, Utrecht University, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, CSI, OASPA, DOAJ, Redalyc-AmeliCA, LIBER, ENRESSH)

³ Ancion, Z., Borrell-Damián, L., Mounier, P., Rooryck, J., & Saenen, B. (2022). Action Plan for Diamond Open Access. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6282403>

declaration (2023), and the Council of the European Union conclusions (2023), which all call for a scholarly publishing ecosystem that is high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable, the hallmarks of Diamond OA.⁴

The idea for a Capacity Centre for Diamond OA was further worked out into a global framework that consists of regional Capacity Hubs (e.g. Redalyc-Amelica in Latin America, African Journals Online [AJOL] in Africa), which in turn coordinate and streamline national, disciplinary, and institutional Diamond OA Capacity Centres, publishers, and service providers.⁵ At the global level, UNESCO is now coordinating the effort to align regional Diamond OA Capacity Hubs and has carried out a survey to develop a worldwide framework for Diamond OA.

The European Diamond Capacity Hub: scope and mission

In Europe, the DIAMAS landscape report (Armengou et al. 2023) provided a detailed mapping of the institutional publishing landscape within the European Research Area (ERA). It highlighted the diversity of practices and capacities, as well as a strong interest in collaborating on technical infrastructure, support services, and communication.

The DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA (<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>) projects developed the building blocks for a regional OA Publishing Capacity Centre that was launched as the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH, <https://diamas.org/>) on 15 January 2025 in Madrid. The vision of the EDCH is to develop a strong, coordinated, and sustainable Diamond OA publishing ecosystem in Europe.

Its mission is to support European national, institutional, and disciplinary Capacity Centres in their activities on Diamond OA scholarly publishing by providing them with coordination, sustainability, technical tools, and services at scale. 15 National Capacity Centres (NCCs) are either operating or being created in various European countries to coordinate Diamond OA initiatives at this level.

The EDCH offers six services to institutional nonprofit Open Access publishers and service providers that are aimed at aligning (1) quality, (2) editorial training, (3) community exchanges, (4) nonprofit OA journals and books visibility, (5) best practices, and (6) publishing tools (see Figure 1).

⁴ UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science: <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMF8546>;
G7 Science and Technology Ministers declaration

https://www8.cao.go.jp/cstp/kokusaiteki/g7_2023/230513_g7_communique.pdf

Council of the European Union Conclusions: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>

⁵ Redalyc- Amelica: <https://www.redalyc.org/> ; African Journals Online: <https://www.ajol.info>

 DIAMOND Discovery Hub	<p>The authoritative list of Diamond OA journals that satisfy the 6 operational criteria of Diamond OA</p>		
 Resources & Guidelines	<p>A living toolsuite bringing together articles and descriptions of best practices on how to manage Diamond OA publishing</p>		
 Publishing Tools	<p>Digital resources, interoperability tools, publishing software enhancements, and add-ons.</p>		

Figure 1: The six services of the EDCH

The DIAMAS project launched the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS, Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024), accompanied by Toolsuite Articles (Armengou et al., 2024a), Guidelines (Armengou et al., 2024b) and Sustainability Resources (Hughes, 2025). CRAFT-OA contributed the design and framework for the Diamond Discovery Hub (Varakhina and Bargheer, 2025), as well as publishing software enhancements. The CRAFT-OA Publishers’ Living Handbook of Diamond OA will be integrated into Resources & Guidelines. Both DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA produced modules and curricula for a Training Platform service (Delvalle and Jan, 2025).

2. Conceptual design

The Diamond OA publishing landscape in Europe is rich and varied, involving many types of organisations and professionals. To ensure that the EDCH services and platforms meet the needs of these stakeholders, consortium partners evaluated the relevance of the EDCH services and components to the roles of each stakeholder group, as well as to specific challenges in terms of information, guidance, and networking.

2.1 Stakeholders

The conceptual design of the EDCH was based on researching the potential use of the infrastructure by the stakeholder groups previously identified as target audiences for the project's communication and engagement activities (Blake et al. 2023):

1. Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSP) and Institutional Publishing Technology Providers (IPTP): this group includes entities providing services, infrastructure, or technologies –such as software, hardware, platforms for scholarly publishing. IPSPs form the technical and operational backbone of Diamond OA. They manage publishing workflows, support editorial quality, ensure compliance with policies and standards, and enable the sustainability and capacity-building of community-led publishing.

2. Learned Societies: organisations that promote specific academic disciplines or professional fields. Many act as publishers, maintain editorial standards, peer review processes, and disciplinary best practices. Some learned societies also operate their own publishing platforms or collaborate with other IPSPs and IPTPs, serving as key stewards of academic integrity and disciplinary identity.

3. Libraries: libraries often host university presses, manage institutional repositories, and serve as facilitators of scholarly communication. Libraries support both the strategic and technical aspects of publishing and play a critical role in policy implementation, capacity building, and coordination at either institutional or national levels.

4. Research Performing Organisations (RPOs): institutions such as universities and public or private research institutes that carry out research. Many are owners and hosts of IPSPs and presses, providing publishing infrastructure and services, and play a critical role in shaping research assessment practices to support OA.

5. Researchers: Researchers include networks, research groups or individuals who are publishers, authors, disseminators or reviewers, and whose published research outputs are assessed. Additionally, teaching staff or readers, learners, either as authors or as readers, postdoc and undergraduate students.

6. Funders: this stakeholder category includes government agencies, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) that fund internal research and publishing activities, as well as Sponsors and Donors. Funders support research and have the potential to financially support non-commercial publishing infrastructures, including Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs).

7. Policymakers: agencies and organisations who develop, implement, or monitor policies on Open Access, Open Science (OS), and research assessment. They include research ministries, RFOs, RPOs, or umbrella organisations at local, national, and international levels who help create the policy environment that enables Diamond OA.

8. Research Assessment Agencies: bodies or departments of ministries or funding organisations responsible for evaluating the quality and impact of research. Their evaluations influence funding decisions, institutional rankings, and science policies. Their role is crucial because the criteria they apply in assessment can support Open Access publishing models.

This stakeholder mapping indicates that most institutions hold multiple, overlapping roles within the scholarly publishing ecosystem. They are often simultaneously involved in delivering publishing services, while contributing to the development and implementation of policies, funding schemes, and research assessment frameworks (see Annex 1). Their multifaceted engagement—as producers, service providers, and evaluators of research—is supported by a wide range of professionals working across publishing operations, institutional support services, and policy design.

Thus, a central objective of the EDCH’s conceptual design was to identify and engage individuals as potential users of its services, as a first step towards the development of an active community of practice around Diamond OA. This active engagement is intended to consolidate the EDCH’s role as a community-driven, collectively supported infrastructure for institutional Diamond OA publishing. Methodologically, the relevance of its resources and services was assessed through a series of use cases based on identified needs and activities of specific professional roles, aligned with the broader stakeholder categories.

2.2 Use cases

The identification of use cases for the EDCH helped the project interpret the EDCH’s overall scope and objectives into a set of meaningful services, by capturing how different stakeholders and professionals would interact with the EDCH components in specific contexts. As part of the conceptual design, the use cases provided insight into challenges and priorities and suggested ways to produce and link tools and resources

that are relevant, practical and responsive to day-to-day operations and decision-making processes.

To support this process, dedicated writing teams were asked to identify key user profiles within each of the suggested stakeholder groups, to describe the needs and priorities associated with each profile and help the designing of user workflows and functionalities across the EDCH components. The teams were coordinated by lead authors with in-depth knowledge of the respective stakeholder communities, and were guided by the following set of questions designed to capture the needs and expectations of potential users:

1. **What are the main professional roles and user profiles within each stakeholder category, and what are their core responsibilities?**
Scope: developing relevant and targeted use cases, based on the roles and activities of potential users
2. **What are the main challenges that the key stakeholders face?**
Scope: understand the structural, technical, financial, or organisational challenges that different stakeholders encounter, and ensure the EDCH provides relevant resources and guidance
3. **What are their goals for using the portal?**
Scope: align the portal's functionalities with user motivations and prioritise features and services accordingly.
4. **What are their expectations upon accessing the portal?**
Scope: inform the design, navigation, and content structuring.
5. **What features would help meet these expectations?**
Scope: identify functional requirements (e.g. search, resource tagging) and ensure that the future development of the EDCH remains responsive to user needs.
6. **What services and resource types (e.g. guidelines, documentation, training material) do they need from the portal?**
Scope: design the EDCH as a dynamic service infrastructure and identify supporting materials that allow users to build capacity.
7. **How often are they expected to use the portal?**
Scope: identify functional requirements (e.g. search, resource tagging) and ensure that the future development of the EDCH remains responsive to user needs.
8. **How likely are they to promote the portal in their communities and beyond?**
Scope: assess the potential for organic dissemination and adoption by each stakeholder group.

To facilitate comparative analysis across use cases, the writing teams were provided with a standardised template (see Annex 2) with the following structural elements:

- **Title:** an outline of the use case context
- **Key actor:** the professional profile of the user
- **Roles:** the user's function and mission within a stakeholder/institution, as defined in the previous section
- **Context:** a real-world scenario in which the user encounters a specific need or challenge
- **Challenges:** factors (e.g. resource constraints, lack of guidance or expertise) that motivate the user to seek support
- **Type of information/guidance needed:** the types of resources or guidance the user seeks to find in the EDCH
- **Types of services:** selected from a predefined list of the services offered by the EDCH
- **Workflow:** mapping of the user's interaction with available resources through the components
- **Features and functionalities:** developments and elements of the EDCH that would support the suggested workflows
- **Relevant component(s):** specific modules or components within the infrastructure relevant to the use case
- **Success scenario:** A brief narrative presenting an ideal outcome that meets the user's needs

A summary of the use cases per stakeholder category and professional profiles is presented below:

2.2.1. IPSP/ IPTP

1. **Flipping a journal to Diamond:** A journal publisher or a journal editorial board is considering transitioning a journal to a Diamond OA and seeks guidance and support.
2. **Launching a new Diamond journal:** An IPSP manager or editorial board is setting up a new Diamond OA journal and needs help navigating standards, workflows, and author engagement
3. **Addressing the loss of funding for a small IPSP:** A small IPSP loses its main funding source and needs help identifying sustainable business models and funding opportunities.
4. **Benchmarking against best practices:** The management team of an IPSP/IPTP wants to assess whether its practices align with international standards and to improve its operational quality.
5. **Streamlining IPSP operations:** An IPSP that faces inefficiencies due to scattered resources and duplicated efforts is looking for centralised tools and information.

6. **Supporting IPSP networks and associations:** A national or regional association of Diamond OA publishers seeks resources and tools to guide members and promote collaboration.
7. **Sharing community resources:** IPSPs/IPTPs wish to contribute existing tools or materials to a shared platform but need guidance on how to do so effectively and get recognition.

Analysis: IPSPs, journal editors, and related stakeholders face a range of challenges that limit their capacity to operate effectively. A recurring issue in the use cases is the lack of financial, technical, and human resources, which affects both established initiatives as well as initiatives under planning. It is evident that IPSPs struggle to navigate standards, training resources, and have limited access to sustainable funding. The dispersion of resources across languages and platforms also leads to duplicated efforts and inefficiencies, making it difficult for IPSPs to identify and align with best practices.

Consequently, there is a clear need for training materials, self-assessment tools, and up-to-date documentation that enables decision-making and capacity building. Moreover, IPSPs are seeking venues that enable knowledge exchange, directories of reliable partners, and mechanisms for networking to strengthen their position and roles within the Diamond OA landscape.

2.2.2. Learned Societies

1. **Learned Society migrates to Diamond OA:** The board of a learned society decides to transition to OA, but lacks technical knowledge, infrastructure, and confidence in retaining members without a print edition.
2. **Continuation of a publication series:** An international society publishes a journal/series of proceedings funded by memberships and library subscriptions. They are exploring a transition to a non-commercial model while ensuring income, maintaining layout quality, and fairly compensating editorial work.
3. **Funding journals in a disciplinary field:** STEM-focused learned societies struggle with decreasing funding. As most existing journals are run through commercial or hybrid OA models, they seek evidence and advocacy tools to push for non-commercial or Diamond OA alternatives.
4. **Keeping up to date with best practices:** National umbrella organisations support multiple societies and liaise with ministries and international bodies. They need tools, communication channels, and up-to-date resources to stay aligned with publishing best practices and the evolving needs of their member societies.

Analysis: the use cases highlight a range of needs and challenges faced by learned societies and their umbrella organisations as they navigate the transition to sustainable, non-commercial OA publishing. Common issues include lack of technical expertise,

inadequate funding, reliance on voluntary work, and limited awareness of viable OA models—especially in non-English or STEM contexts where commercial publishers dominate. Societies also face uncertainty about maintaining quality, member engagement, and continuity of publications during the shift to OA. National umbrella organisations often lack comprehensive information about their member societies' needs and struggle to stay current with best practices.

2.2.3. Libraries

1. **Supporting Diamond OA:** A library director seeks strategic guidance, advocacy tools, and an overview of Diamond OA to align institutional policies and make informed resource allocations.
2. **Evaluating publishing operations:** A manager of a library-based university press needs benchmarking tools, peer connections, and operational guidance to improve services and comply with evolving standards.
3. **Communicating Diamond OA to researchers:** Library support staff is looking for myth-busting materials, training modules, and advocacy tools to better inform researchers about Diamond OA.
4. **Creating a national Diamond OA catalogue:** A national library aims to build a public, accessible catalogue of national Diamond OA solutions and improve digital preservation and discoverability.
5. **Funding Diamond OA:** Budget holders and negotiators for institutional acquisitions want to understand how to redirect subscription budgets and explore collaborative funding models to support Diamond OA at scale.
6. **Promoting OA awareness:** Management of a national library or an institution responsible for hosting a national platform seeks access to training resources, strategies, and guidelines for promoting OA awareness among librarians.
7. **Establishing a Capacity Centre:** Management of a national or institutional initiative explores setting up a central support hub to coordinate OA publishing efforts and offer guidance to other institutions.

Analysis: Libraries often face challenges in supporting and advancing Diamond OA. A major barrier is the lack of internal expertise, which limits their ability to stay informed on evolving practices or invest time in optimising workflows. Moreover, relevant information and resources are often fragmented, outdated, or not tailored to their specific needs. This makes it difficult for both management and staff to maintain a clear overview of ongoing initiatives and developments. These difficulties are often complemented by institutional resistance, as leadership may not fully understand the value or cost of Diamond OA.

Technical and publishing teams supporting publishing initiatives within libraries require practical, hands-on tools—such as self-assessment frameworks, best practice documentation, and recommendations for software to improve operational efficiency, ensure compliance with standards, and explore collaborative infrastructure options.

2.2.4. Research Performing Organisations (RPO)

1. **Design a comprehensive OA strategy:** The institutional leaders of an RPO plan to revise the institution's OA publication policy. They need reliable information and guidance to define goals, allocate funding, build support systems, and manage a cultural shift toward Diamond OA publishing.
2. **Setting up an OA publishing service:** An RPO wants to establish a sustainable, high-quality OA publishing service. The administration of the research affairs department and the support staff face several challenges (limited awareness, concerns about OA quality, need for training and researchers' engagement), and seek a centralised hub providing access to resources and services.
3. **Diversify book publishing activities:** An RPO that collaborates with commercial publishers for book series aims to transition to OA. The RPO does not have the staff or the technical knowledge and infrastructure to act as a Publisher for books, and needs support in restructuring the institution and the allocation of resources.

Analysis: The use cases illustrate the interrelated needs and challenges RPOs face as they engage with or transition to OA publishing: lack of technical expertise, funding constraints, limited awareness of Diamond OA models, institutional resistance, and structural barriers such as reward systems tied to traditional publishing. Institutional leaders seek strategic guidance to develop comprehensive OA policies and services. There is also a growing need to diversify book publishing in alignment with OA goals.

2.2.5. Researchers

1. **Finding a Diamond OA publisher:** An editorial team wants to move their journal to a Diamond OA publisher and is searching for a suitable IPSP.
2. **Upgrading a standalone journal:** An editorial board managing an OA journal seeks guidance to ensure sustainability and improve their operational model. They face limited funding, lack of personnel, and workflow inefficiencies.
3. **Researcher looking for training or capacity building:** a researcher is unfamiliar with Diamond OA publishing and needs guidance and training to understand Diamond OA principles
4. **Researcher planning to publish in a Diamond OA journal:** a researcher is seeking a Diamond OA publisher and/or a journal that publishes on a specific disciplinary field.

Analysis: The use cases illustrate the diverse needs of researchers, both as authors and as members of editorial teams involved in Diamond OA publishing. Editorial boards often require practical support to launch new journals, ensure the sustainability of existing journals, or enhance their operations. At the same time, individual researchers face barriers when trying to publish their work through Diamond OA channels - mainly due to the limited visibility of Diamond OA publishers and journals, as well as a lack of clear guidance on key operational aspects such as open access policies, licensing, and quality standards.

2.2.6. Funders

1. **Empowering institutional leadership for OA advancements:** Institutional leaders seek evidence and arguments to promote Diamond OA within scientific publishing reforms. They need examples of viable alternatives to traditional publishing models to shape policy and redirect funds.
2. **Funder seeking guidance to issue/update an OA policy:** Funders developing or updating OA policies require tools to assess the value and standards of Diamond OA, including quality indicators and compliance with technical and policy standards.
3. **Funder wishes to fund Diamond OA:** Funders want authoritative information about who needs funding in Diamond OA publishing, including data on infrastructure, platforms, and financial needs, to make informed investment decisions.
4. **Institutional leadership wishing to invest or save costs:** An institutional leader seeks an overview of their institution's publishing landscape and guidance to reduce duplication, identify cost-saving opportunities, and streamline support for internal OA publishing efforts.
5. **Developing a sustainability framework:** A Funder/Sponsor/Donor (FSD) wants to implement actionable recommendations to improve IPSP sustainability, in order to enhance the quality and sustainability of institutional publishing services and seeks strategic guidance and relevant data.

Analysis: There is a shared need among Funders, Sponsors and Donors for authoritative, accessible information to support evidence-based funding decisions and policy development for Diamond OA publishing. Funders face challenges such as limited visibility into the quality and sustainability of institutional publishing services, uncertainty about what and whom to fund, and a lack of standardised data on journal compliance, infrastructure, and financial needs. They also seek guidance on how to assess OA initiatives' impact and align investments with broader research reform goals.

2.2.7. Policymakers

1. **Overview of national OA Diamond publishing:** A Ministry of Research/Education, and/or the leadership of a national OS coordination body need documentation and resources to assess the national Diamond OA landscape to inform strategic planning and policy development.
2. **Adapting best practices to national contexts:** Umbrella organisations such as national Academies or scholarly associations seek adaptable international best practices, policies, and training materials to support national scholarly communication, infrastructure development, and policy alignment.

Analysis: The use cases for policymakers highlight a need for reliable, up-to-date data and adaptable guidance to inform national strategies on Diamond OA publishing. Policymakers often lack a clear understanding of the scope, cost structures, and positioning of Diamond OA within the broader publishing ecosystem, as well as insights into the effectiveness of current national efforts. Challenges include fragmented data, limited capacity to benchmark against international practices, and difficulty in translating general best practices into context-specific policy actions.

2.2.8. Research Assessment Agencies (RAA)

1. **Addressing challenges in research assessment for OA:** A RAA must understand the influence of Diamond OA on research quality, dissemination, and academic progress. Information is needed on strategies to evaluate the impact and quality of OA content.
2. **Rethinking research assessment for OA Promotion:** A Research Assessment Unit within a RPO seeks to recognise the influence of OA on research quality, dissemination, and academic advancement, considering various aspects of research and valuing the work of professionals involved in editing (many of whom are researchers).
3. **Supporting researchers in evaluation committees:** Researchers in evaluation committees face challenges related to understanding (and trusting) the quality and significance of Diamond OA publications. Clear explanations and resources on the concept and benefits of Diamond OA and guidelines on evaluating the quality and impact of OA publications are needed.

Analysis: The use cases related to research assessment reveal a need for more inclusive, transparent, and context-sensitive evaluation frameworks that recognise the value of diverse publishing models, particularly Diamond OA. Current systems often disadvantage institutional and non-commercial publishing efforts. Key challenges include a lack of awareness about the quality and legitimacy of Diamond OA outputs, limited infrastructure to track and assess their contributions, and misalignment

between assessment criteria and OS goals.

2.3 Design principles

The use cases identified several important challenges for institutions and individuals involved in Diamond OA publishing:

- Limited resources: Many organisations lack the financial and technical capacity to build and maintain publishing services that can meet evolving standards and expectations.
- Fragmentation: Efforts and tools are often scattered or duplicated, with some areas of Diamond OA lacking any support or guidance.
- Lack of visibility: There is no clear picture of the Diamond OA landscape, making it difficult for stakeholders to collaborate, align their efforts, or exchange knowledge and information. This also makes it harder for funders and policymakers to provide consistent, long-term support.

Another key finding is that many organisations involved in Diamond OA—such as RPOs, learned societies, and publishing platforms—often take on multiple roles at once. They may act as publishers, funders, and policy advocates simultaneously. As a result, their needs are complex and interconnected.

To overcome these challenges, stakeholders need easy access to reliable, up-to-date information. This includes legal, financial, and policy guidance, as well as real-world examples of successful initiatives. Clear and reusable training materials—especially for editorial workflows, metadata, and OA policies—are also essential for building internal skills and supporting others involved in the publishing process.

Beyond information, there is also a strong need for services that promote collaboration and shared learning. These include peer exchange networks and access to shared infrastructure and registries. Communities are looking for interactive spaces where they can get support, connect with peers, and learn from each other's experiences.

Based on the analysis of the use cases and continuous feedback received from stakeholders at networking events, the following design principles were identified as the foundational framework for the EDCH:

1. To address the current fragmentation, the EDCH should ensure easy access to high-quality, reliable, and up-to-date resources supporting both skills and institutional development; it should also serve as a dynamic hub where stakeholders can connect, share experiences, and build capacity.

2. The EDCH should be interoperable with existing and future Capacity Centres and infrastructures, and support federated services and tools addressing diverse workflows and models.
3. By maintaining transparent governance and a robust operational plan, the EDCH should be conceived as a sustainable infrastructure, adaptive to emerging needs and standards.
4. Additionally, it should be co-developed with the communities it serves, ensuring responsiveness to evolving needs. It should allow for modular adoption and regional customisation, making it suitable for different contexts and levels of maturity.

3. Services and Components

The decisions taken regarding the overall design of the EDCH and the implementation of its components were grounded in stakeholder input and detailed analysis of the use cases, ensuring that the infrastructure would respond to the activities, needs and challenges faced by the Diamond OA community. A foundational step was to define a core set of six services offered by the EDCH, which served as the backbone for implementing the EDCH as a federated infrastructure of interoperable components.

This federated approach allows components to be developed, hosted, and maintained by different institutions, while ensuring that the infrastructure operates as a unified service. A corresponding governance and operational framework, presented in the following section, was put in place to enable coordinating participation from institutions. This framework also supports distributed responsibility and aligns with the principle of collective ownership of the Hub. It also facilitates the future scaling of the infrastructure, with operational tasks being shared across institutions.

In alignment with the participatory governance scheme, the EDCH has been conceptualised as an extensible infrastructure, allowing for the future integration of additional services and/or components. To strengthen transparency and allow other initiatives to replicate, adapt, or contribute to the infrastructure, open-source solutions were prioritised whenever feasible. The implementation of the components was carefully documented, and both the codebase and architectural framework are made gradually available on a dedicated GitHub organisation.⁶

The following services and components have been developed:

3.1 Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)

DOAS (Consortium of the Diamas project, 2024) is an instrument that helps foster quality assurance in Diamond OA publishing. DOAS includes both a practical guide and benchmarking resources for checking quality and sustainability. DOAS is based on the seven core components of scholarly publishing outlined in the *Action Plan for Diamond Open Access* (Ancion et al. 2022), which were subsequently revised and modified by the DIAMAS project team. These are:

1. Funding
2. Legal ownership, mission and governance

⁶ <https://github.com/orgs/EUDCH/repositories>

3. Open Science
4. Editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity
5. Technical service efficiency
6. Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact
7. Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB), multilingualism and gender equity

Compliance against the DOAS recommendations can be assessed via the online DOAS self-assessment tool (<https://diamas.fecyt.es/>). This self-assessment tool consists of two parallel instances (DOAS self-assessment and Diamond OA Sustainability check) that can be completed sequentially, if desired. It has been designed to provide a structured online workflow for Diamond OA publishers and Diamond OA service providers who wish to analyse their level of operational capacity and sustainability.

The DOAS and self-assessment tool allow Diamond OA Publishers and Providers to assess their compliance with the seven quality components of DOAS, as well as their financial sustainability.

3.2 Resources and Guidelines

A set of resources that support publishers moving towards Diamond OA. They include concise high-level introductions to Diamond OA and to DOAS as well as guidelines and good practices for journal publishing.

The resources are published on a dedicated component of the EDCH (<https://toolsuite.diamas.org>), which offers detailed instructions and practical guidance to assist Diamond OA publishers in meeting the standards outlined in the DOAS. The resources, -composing 14 high-level articles and 18 guidelines on specific topics and workflows- are complemented by a glossary of terms used, keywords and frequently asked questions (FAQs) in order to support users in navigating across their content. A dedicated section presents a suite of resources for publishers, service providers and funders to support the sustainability of institutional publishing.

In addition, the online platform acts as a signpost to other DIAMAS project outputs and external resources.

3.3. Registry and Forum

The Registry (<https://registry.diamas.org/>) and Forum (<https://forum.diamas.org/>) serve as the two core components of the IPSP/IPTP network (Paulhac et al, 2025). They are virtual spaces dedicated to fostering collaboration and networking among Diamond OA community members. They provide a place where services, challenges, and solutions can be presented and discussed.

The Registry is the main gateway to the network. It offers an overview of the organisations that are part of the community, highlighting their services and operational capabilities. It helps stakeholders understand who is involved in the network and the areas of expertise of each member institution.

The Forum is an interactive online space where members of the broader Diamond OA community can meet, collaborate, and share experiences. The Forum allows participants to build partnerships, exchange best practices, and engage in discussions about common challenges and opportunities. It supports both structured collaboration and informal conversations that help strengthen the interaction of the community.

3.4. Training platform

The Training Platform (<https://training.diamas.org/>) is dedicated to helping IPSPs and IPTPs enhance their skills and build capacity by offering skill-building training modules and curricula in various areas.

The Training Platform offers a complete, structured set of learning resources, designed to help learners achieve specific objectives and impart skills and knowledge to a defined audience. The training programme comprises 34 training materials, organised into courses focusing on the elements of DOAS. It is primarily intended for learners at an elementary level, aiming to provide a comprehensive introduction to principles and practices through diverse learning approaches (interactive courses, infographics, simulated conversations and self-reflection tools).

3.5 Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)

The Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH, <https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/>) is a core output of the CRAFT-OA project. It aims to provide an authoritative list of Diamond OA journals in Europe, helping these journals increase their visibility in the academic community and beyond.

Through the DDH, Diamond OA journals become part of a collection of journals applying the Diamond model, and reach recognition for their diamond effort, while Publishers and Service Providers can support their journals by getting their data aligned, improved and harmonised for broader dissemination.

3.6 Publishing tools

Publishing Tools refers to a set of software tools, add-ons and other technical developments that serve to improve technical efficiency at the level of publishing

workflows and platforms. The publishing tools also furnish the necessary components to ensure seamless interoperability between various publishing software solutions.

Publishing Tools comprise a collection of materials and instructions that specifically address the needs of OJS users (e.g. <https://github.com/munipress/disco/tree/ojs-3-2-0>), covering both pre-installation decisions and workflows for installation and upgrade. The Tools will eventually support a fully operational OJS preconfiguration that will be developed to support nonprofit OA publishing services and their technical alignment with the DOAS recommendations.

4. Governance and operational framework

From an operational perspective, the EDCH is established as a collective of organisations that publicly express their intention to financially support, coordinate and align Diamond OA scholarly publishing in Europe. It includes member organisations and institutions that fund and/or contribute to the development and maintenance of the EDCH (see Annex 3). Member organisations must be public or not-for-profit organisations whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship. These include, but are not limited to, RPOs, RFOs, research institutes, and scholarly societies that can make substantial financial contributions to the operations of the EDCH. The EDCH is not legally incorporated: OPERAS AISBL operates as the fiscal host of the EDCH. A legal entity can be founded at a later stage, by decision of the Assembly.

4.1 Membership

The EDCH has three types of members:

1. **Supporting Members:** Public or non-profit organisations (e.g. charities, foundations, associations, RFOs, RPOs) located in the European Research Area (ERA) whose legal mission is to fund and/ or perform research and scholarship.
2. **Operational Members:** National and international organisations that are engaged in aspects of Diamond OA publishing, and willing to provide long-term services to EDCH and/or leading essential EDCH Task Forces.
3. **Community members:** Diamond Capacity Centres, Diamond Publishers, Diamond Service Providers, Diamond Tools & Technology Providers as well as advocacy organisations promoting Diamond OA. Community Member organisations must be registered members of the EDCH Registry.

Supporting Members who wish to join EDCH must be willing to make a substantial financial contribution to EDCH. Supporting members can flag a percentage of their contribution to a specific Task Force, within limits to be determined. Supporting members will join the EDCH *Steering Committee*.

Operational Members who wish to join EDCH must be willing to take on long-term responsibility for and make in-kind contributions to at least one substantial Task Force that contributes to the goals of EDCH. They will join the EDCH *Executive Committee*.

Community Members will join the EDCH *Assembly*. The EDCH Assembly members elect two co-chairs who will be members of the Steering Committee.

4.2 Governance

The EDCH Assembly

The EDCH Assembly will be consulted by the Executive Committee on various Diamond initiatives and be informed of EDCH activities. The EDCH Assembly members elect two co-chairs who will be members of the Steering Committee.

The EDCH Steering Committee

The EDCH Steering Committee is composed of the Chair (currently Lidia Borrell-Damián); the two Co-chairs of the EDCH Assembly; the (Co-)coordinator(s) of EDCH who participate as non-voting Observers (currently Pierre Mounier and Johan Rooryck); the Representatives of the Supporting Members, and an Observer elected by the non-European members of the Diamond Action Plan Community.

The EDCH Steering Committee takes all major decisions regarding EDCH principles, services, Task Forces, and functions, including approving any amendments and providing guidance on their implementation. The Steering Committee approves changes to the EDCH Terms of Reference. It appoints the (Co-)coordinator(s) and the Steering Committee for a (renewable) term of office of one year; the recruitment of the (Co-)coordinator(s) can be delegated to a search/nomination committee appointed by the Chair of the EDCH Assembly. The Steering Committee approves the multiannual strategy, the annual budget and work plan as proposed by the Executive Committee. Finally, Steering Committee members promote the EDCH and recruit additional member organisations and support for EDCH.

All members joining EDCH must be willing to collaborate in a coordinated manner with other members towards the goals of EDCH. Members can combine the roles of Supporting and Operational members, with a seat in both the Steering and the Executive Committees, if they make both financial and in-kind contributions to the EDCH.

The EDCH Executive Committee

The EDCH Executive Committee is composed of the (Co-)coordinator(s) of the EDCH and the Representatives of the Operational Members. The (Co-)coordinator(s) chair the Executive Committee.

The EDCH Executive Committee coordinates, implements and executes the EDCH strategy, time plan, and allocate resources after approval by the Steering Committee. The Executive Committee communicates with the fiscal host of EDCH, OPERAS and to the outside on behalf of EDCH; liaises with other relevant stakeholders and organisations; and aligns, develops, and curates the various services of the EDCH.

The Executive Committee approves spending commitments resulting from calls for tender and follow-up on contract execution that fall within the annual work plan and strategy.

The Executive Committee provides expertise and input to all questions and proposals submitted to them by the Steering Committee.

Executive Committee Members lead Task Forces and other relevant projects to further the success of EDCH. They support and brief their own organisations and liaise with other parts of their organisation involved in the functioning of EDCH; and can be consulted by other Task Forces or working groups, as relevant. They work closely with the Diamond OA Capacity Centres.

The (Co-)coordinator(s) for EDCH lead the Executive Committee and are also non-voting members of the EDCH Steering Committee. They are responsible for developing strategic input to the Steering Committee. They act as the main spokesperson(s) for EDCH, liaise with the Diamond Capacity Centres, the Diamond OA Global Alliance, and with other stakeholder groups, and promote Diamond OA and the EDCH in order to gain support from new organisations. With the support of the Community Manager(s) the (Co-)coordinator(s) develop and supervise the implementation of the EDCH Coordination Team work plan.

4.3 Task Forces

The overall objective of the six EDCH Task Forces is to support the EDCH's activities, further develop its services, and thereby support the EDCH's sustainability. Provisionally coordinated by members of the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA consortia, the Task Forces work collaboratively to ensure the EDCH remains efficient and serves as an inclusive venue for the Diamond OA community in the ERA.

4.3.1. Community Task Force

Coordinators: OPERAS, EIFL

The Community Task Force aims to establish a community of practice around Diamond OA publishing. Its activities promote collaboration among Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools and Technology Providers, with the objective of aligning efforts and streamlining operations to enhance efficiency and impact. Coordinated by OPERAS and EIFL, the Task Force supports the Registry and the Forum of the European Diamond Capacity Hub, as the two EDCH components that offer comprehensive, up-to-date information about organisations involved in Diamond OA, and foster interaction across the community, respectively

Through its activities, the Community Task Force seeks to strengthen connections and build partnerships across the Diamond OA landscape in Europe. Following the launch of the EDCH, the main priority of the Task Force is to establish a broad and active network of Capacity Centres across Europe (see section 4.4).

4.3.2. Diamondisation Task Force

Collectively coordinated

'Diamondisation' is a cover term for all actions that help transition scholarly outputs (journals, books, preprints, data, peer reviews) to a Diamond OA model.

The Diamondisation Task Force will establish a fund to help Diamond Capacity Centres and Service Providers transition scholarly outputs to Diamond OA. The Diamondisation Task Force will evaluate applications by Capacity Centres and Service Providers to transition outputs in the sense defined above.

Diamondisation efforts that are in scope for this Task Force include the following:

1. Transitioning scholarly disciplines lacking Diamond OA options.
2. Transitioning existing subscription journals.
3. Transitioning existing journal communities.
4. Transitioning outputs other than journals.

4.3.3. Funding Task Force

Coordinators: ANR, OPERAS, SPARC Europe

The goal of the funding Task Force is to help the EDCH coordinators raise funds in the mid to long-term. The Task Force will use a stakeholder-targeted approach to explore funding opportunities before setting up communication strategies and annual work plans; it will also establish key messaging and processes to speak to potential funders be they institutions, research agencies, charities, government or others.

The Funding Task Force works closely with the DIAMAS and ALMASI (<https://almasiproject.org/>) projects to seek synergies and utilise capacities. As part of this framework, it considers sustaining the EDCH as part of the wider scholarly publishing and research data ecosystem, including international services and infrastructure, such as Open Research Europe (ORE) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

4.3.4. Quality Alignment Task Force

Coordinators: FECYT, DOAJ

The Quality Alignment Task Force is coordinated by FECYT and DOAJ, and focuses on ensuring that scholarly publishing and research communication are rigorous and transparent. The Task Force's primary goal is to promote DOAS as a benchmark for transparency and rigour. By addressing current disparities in open access, the Task Force aims to build a high-quality, inclusive and collaborative environment where quality is seen as a public good.

The work to be done in this Task Force includes:

1. Raising awareness about DOAS through outreach campaigns
2. Promoting the use of the DOAS through the Self-Assessment Tool
3. Collaborating on translations of the DOAS document
4. Setting up discussion forums on new developments, for example, the integration of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI)

These efforts aim to promote equitable knowledge sharing and improve standards in OA publishing.

4.3.5. Skills and Competences Task Force

Coordinator: OpenEdition, Jisc

The purpose of the Skills and Competences Task Force is to enhance capacity in Diamond OA publishing. One of its key roles is to manage and further develop two major components of the EDCH: the Training Platform and the Toolsuite.

Through the Toolsuite, the Task Force will manage resources that support Diamond OA and DOAS, including a set of high-level articles, in-depth guidelines, and links to self-assessment tools, training materials, and other resources. One of the main activities of this Task Force is also to provide a learning management system hosting tailored training materials for users of the EDCH and supporting the community in implementing training autonomously.

4.3.6. Tools and Technologies Task Force

Coordinators: OPERAS, DOAJ

The Tools and Technologies Task Force is dedicated to advancing technical excellence and fostering collaboration within the Diamond OA community, ensuring sustainability and innovation for the future. The Task Force is providing technical tools and services

that ensure interoperability and compliance across systems. It also supports and advises technical coordination within the EDCH initiative, fostering collaboration and innovation in the field.

The Task Force builds upon the outputs of the CRAFT-OA project and works to identify additional tools and technologies relevant to the Diamond publishing lifecycle, including solutions for authoring, peer-review tracking, publishing, indexing, dissemination and preservation, among others. It also advises EDCH on emerging technologies, such as the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Diamond OA.

4.4 National Capacity Centres (NCC) network

In June 2025, at the final DIAMAS conference in Brussels, an initial meeting for National Capacity Centres (NCCs) and initiatives aiming to build NCCs took place. The meeting gathered 15 NCCs representing all regions of Europe, thus marking the first concrete step in advancing one of the key objectives of the EDCH Community Task Force: to identify, support, and connect initiatives providing Diamond OA publishing services.

Currently, 11 NCCs are operational, while 8 others are still in development or emerging (see Annex 3). The EDCH's approach is therefore twofold: to reinforce the work of existing NCCs and to support the formalisation or creation of new ones. The overarching goal is to establish a decentralised yet coordinated network of NCCs that can foster and sustain Diamond OA within their respective national and linguistic communities.

The first step in this process is to identify local needs, which will provide crucial insights into the specific conditions for implementing Diamond OA in each context. The EDCH will then collaborate closely with NCCs to co-develop a common action plan covering key areas such as DOAS certification and monitoring, training, deployment of tools, and community engagement.

NCCs will be encouraged to take full advantage of the services and resources offered by the EDCH. In return, they will play a central role in localising and promoting these tools—through translation, adaptation to national frameworks, and alignment with local research assessment systems and open science policies.

To foster collaboration and mutual support, four online coordination meetings will be held annually, complemented by an in-person gathering during the European Diamond OA Festival.

4.5 Communication and branding

Central to EDCH's identity is a branding approach shaped through active collaboration and engagement with its diverse community. Rather than being imposed from the top down, the EDCH evolves through the shared values, insights, and contributions of the

stakeholders it represents. This inclusive process ensures that the visual identity and messaging of EDCH authentically reflect the collective mission and priorities of the Diamond Open Access ecosystem.

The brand identity of the EDCH has been built upon that of the DIAMAS project. In contrast to the diamond in the DIAMAS logo, each facet of the diamond in the EDCH logo has an individual colour. Each service of the EDCH is represented by the colour of a single facet, giving each a distinct logo through its unique position and hue. As in the DIAMAS project, the EDCH uses Barlow, a font licensed under the Open Font License.

A brand sheet for the EDCH with all respective colour codes, font variations and logos is available on the EDCH main website. Additionally, an introductory brochure and a step-by-step guide have been created.⁷

The EDCH website (<https://diamas.org>) serves as the central hub for the EDCH, presenting its scope, activities, governance, and simultaneously, is a pathway to all EDCH services. In January 2025, the EDCH website was launched at the public launch of the EDCH in Madrid.⁸ More than 120 people followed the event, marking the start of official EDCH-led communication and dissemination activities.

Two social media accounts have been created for the EDCH, on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eudch>) and Bluesky (@[eudch@bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/eudch.social)). A YouTube playlist for EDCH content is operated through the OPERAS YouTube channel.⁹ The most important communication and engagement channel is the EDCH Forum. In addition to offering a space for discussion and knowledge exchange, the Forum serves as a central hub where key updates and event announcements are posted via dedicated topics, enabling all community members to stay informed and engaged. An “Upcoming Events” calendar is also available on the Forum, providing a shared overview of webinars, workshops, and meetings related to Diamond OA and, even sometimes more broadly, OA in Europe. It allows members to coordinate participation and maintain a shared view of relevant activities across the community.

⁷ EDCH brandsheet:

<https://diamas.org/sites/default/files/Communication%20Kit/Brand%20Sheet%20EDCH.pdf>

EDCH brochure:

<https://diamas.org/sites/default/files/Communication%20Kit/Brochure%20EDCH%20digital.pdf>

EDCH step-by-step guide: https://diamas.org/sites/default/files/2025-06/EDCH_Step%20by%20step%20kit.pdf

⁸ EDCH public launch presentation:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DNGWQzktzZk&list=PLNSNT11cPt5YFlgG7EyTzsj00-t_Ldvgk&index=3&t=1s

⁹ EDCH Youtube playlist: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNT11cPt5YFlgG7EyTzsj00-t_Ldvgk

5. Further developments and sustainability

The further development and long-term sustainability of the EDCH are in alignment with the conceptual principles outlined in section 2 of the report: as the EDCH evolves, ensuring robust infrastructure, inclusive governance, and sustainable services will become essential to support its mission. This section outlines strategic approaches to secure capacity, resilience, and relevance of the EDCH and its components.

5.1. Funding and organisational consolidation

The EDCH's governance and project-based funding scheme, which supported its activities during the initial phase of its operation, will evolve from 2026 onwards as part of a strategic plan to consolidate its functions and incorporate the lessons learned since its launch.

A formalisation of the relationship between EDCH and its fiscal host, OPERAS AISBL, is an essential step in this process. It involves determining the degree of operational autonomy of the Hub, the distribution of responsibilities, and the monitoring mechanisms that OPERAS AISBL must implement due to its legal obligations. A Memorandum of Understanding addressing these operational aspects is currently being prepared.

Accordingly, the rights and duties of the various parties collaborating within the framework of the EDCH are being established. Terms of Reference for supporting, operational, and community members are to be adopted shortly; moreover, a dedicated Memorandum of Understanding will outline the commitments of operational members regarding the provision of services, tools, or human resources for the coordination of Task Forces.

The membership model for supporting members will also be updated during the year. A distribution of financial contribution levels based on entity types (institutional capacity centre, national capacity centre, funding organisation) and other parameters—such as the average income level of the host country—has yet to be established to ensure fair representation of the various stakeholders in the community.

The financial sustainability of the EDCH will be the subject of a detailed study carried out by a consulting agency in the second half of 2025.

5.2. Community-building

To establish the EDCH as the central platform for Diamond OA in the ERA, the objective is to position it as the go-to hub where key stakeholders actively engage and collaborate.

By creating shared spaces such as the main portal and the interactive Forum, the EDCH aims to foster ongoing dialogue, knowledge exchange, and a sense of community.

A crucial step in this process is defining common values, a shared vision, and a unified mission. These eventually form the foundation of the main narrative around the EDCH and are reflected in all its work, including the EDCH policy on equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging (EDIB) under development.

The community-building strategy focuses on expanding participation across disciplines, languages, and publishing models, the EDCH Registry and Forum being key components in this effort. In line with this, the Registry will be expanded to include book publishers, supporting a wider and more representative Diamond OA publishing community. A dedicated space for Diamond OA books within the Forum will support exchanges among these actors, particularly around DOAS implementation and nation-level strategies.

In parallel, a directory of nonprofit publishing professionals interested in collaboration will be developed, with the ambition of supporting future peer-learning, mobility or mentorship initiatives. This will promote capacity building and facilitate the exchange of expertise across national and institutional boundaries. In the longer term, partnership with existing university alliances and mobility frameworks (such as Erasmus+) will be explored to reinforce sustainability.

To further build visibility and consolidate the European Diamond OA community, the EDCH will continue to organise dedicated events, such as workshops, webinars and networking in-person meetings, to present its service and connect with stakeholders.

To ensure these measures have a meaningful impact within regional and linguistic communities, the EDCH focuses on the development of strong partnerships and networks—such as the NCC network mentioned above—to leverage their reach and effectively support dissemination and engagement.

5.3. Community Engagement

Active community engagement is at the heart of the EDCH. It involves sustaining regular interaction with community members and creating conditions for ongoing contribution and co-creation, particularly through the EDCH Forum.

To maintain an ongoing connection and visibility, the EDCH will implement a regular communication strategy—through social media posts referencing the Forum, news updates, and calls to action—designed to keep the community informed, engaged, and

motivated. Interactive formats such as webinars, Q&A sessions, and workshops will provide opportunities to deepen knowledge, strengthen involvement, and foster meaningful exchange. These activities have already been initiated through DIAMAS (e.g. the DOAS-a-thon, a webinar format presenting DOAS or a standardised format for an introductory webinar to the EDCH Forum & Registry, and Training platform) and will be further developed. In the coming period, special attention will be given to supporting member-led contributions in the Forum and across EDCH activities, to encourage diverse perspectives and peer learning. Contributors will be invited to share use cases, training resources and local implementation strategies.

In alignment with the community-building strategy, a network of national EDCH advocates will also play a role in sustaining engagement at the local level.¹⁰ This will contribute to better engagement within regional communities and allow for more targeted outreach.

Feedback and input from members will be actively sought to inform future activities, shape policies, and ensure the EDCH remains responsive to community needs and priorities. Moreover, the EDCH will encourage member-led contributions, creating space for diverse voices and experiences to enrich the platform and inspire others.

5.4. Technical management

Alignment of the technical management of the EDCH services is a key activity. A lightweight interoperability framework, presented below, will be implemented to this effect.

Service integration and interoperability should not only be addressed by technical means; there is a need to establish an overarching framework, documenting requirements, guidelines, best practices and policies. This activity should build on the expertise of the service providers and other stakeholders. In order to foster discussions, share knowledge, and move forward as a collective, an EDCH service provider forum will be established. Taking into account the feedback from the various stakeholders, the existing roadmaps and plans for the EDCH services, the approach for harmonizing the technical management will be further refined and addressed in multiple phases.

5.4.1 Technical aspects of interoperability

Currently, the following technical aspects have been identified as being relevant for the EDCH:

¹⁰ Call for EDCH advocates: <https://forum.diamas.org/t/join-the-movement-the-edch-is-looking-for-its-advocates/331>

- The **Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)**, which is further described below.
- The **Configuration Management Database (CMDB)**, as the central component of most IT service management systems. The EDCH CMDB will document the inventory of the different assets or key components, and will be the source of trust about the infrastructure components to be consumed by other services. In a distributed infrastructure such as EDCH, with services operated by multiple independent organisations, the capability of a CMDB to document providers, and contact points is instrumental in addressing challenges such as change management when investigating who are the contacts for the services that may be affected by a change, or when coordinating on security related activities.
- **Service monitoring** will be put in place, discovering the different service endpoints to monitor via the CMDB. Service monitoring will start by focusing on the service availability, and could later be expanded to cover telemetry metrics to improve observability¹¹.
- Finally, **end-to-end testing** will be used to test supported use cases, and validate the capacities of the system. Test scenarios will aim at implementing all the requirements identified by the EDCH community, service providers and coordination bodies. These tests may be linked with the work on monitoring to control the service reliability.

At a later stage, it will be evaluated if additional services should be put in place, such as a central helpdesk to support users of the EDCH, or collecting usage data.

5.4.2 Non-technical aspects of interoperability

To enable interoperability, and reach a satisfactory and coherent service quality level, various non-technical aspects have to be investigated and documented. A set of service delivery requirements, policies and best practices will be put in place to harmonise and monitor service delivery across the service providers. These documents will be created considering the needs of relevant stakeholders.

The documentation will cover a broad range of aspects:

- **A security baseline** to define minimum expectations and requirements to establish a satisfactory level of trust between all the EDCH stakeholders. The

¹¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Observability_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Observability_(software))

EOSC Security baseline¹² will be used as an input, to ensure alignment with best practices identified for EOSC.

- **A set of policies** to formulate the minimal set of requirements that should be followed by all stakeholders and provide a framework for the delivery of the services. Capitalising on the *AARC Policy Development Kit*¹³, the policies will include requirements touching different topics such as security, personal data processing, or conditions of use.
- **A set of procedures** to formalise how different activities should be implemented, for example integration with the EDCH AAI, change management or responses to security incidents.
- **A set of agreements**, such as operational level agreements and service level agreements, to formalise the expectations regarding service delivery, and the responsibilities of all parties.
- **A set of best practices** related to source code management, automated testing, backups, update management, monitoring, telemetry, central logging,
- **Assessments and lightweight audits** to provide factual reviews of the services and ensure their compliance with the policy requirements. Their results will be used to identify and suggest improvements.
- **A set of templates**, such as an Acceptable User Policy, and privacy notices, to present important information to the users in a coherent way, improving user experience. These templates will leverage outcomes of other projects and initiatives such as the AARC initiative¹⁴.

In order to support the service providers and expand knowledge, relevant documentation and training resources will be collected on a shared online location. Training actions may also be conducted as appropriate to cover different aspects (such as IT Service Management with FitSM).¹⁵

At a later stage, in alignment with the identified requirements and priorities, formal processes may be put in place to address workflows such as service level management or change management, consolidating the existing policies and procedures.

5.4.3 Towards the implementation of an EDCH AAI

5.4.3.1 Federated Access

Authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) is an essential part of technical design; it allows users to access the services, protect their data, and helps service

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/7396725>

¹³ <https://aarc-community.org/policy/policy-development-kit/>

¹⁴ <https://aarc-community.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

providers to manage access. Federated access mechanisms are now used by major European research infrastructures. In 2015, the Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC) initiative was launched to address the need for federated access to e-infrastructures. A major outcome of the AARC project¹⁶ is the *AARC Blueprint Architecture* (AARC BPA)¹⁷, and a set of supporting guidelines. The AARC BPA (see figure 2), is a set of building blocks that can be combined to implement customised federated access management solutions.

Figure 2: The AARC Blueprint Architecture

Due to the involvement of multiple entities, service providers, identity providers, and proxy services allowing users to select an identity provider, Federated Access is more complex than centralised access. To mitigate the complexities at the level of the EDCH, the following measures will be implemented:

¹⁶ <https://aarc-community.org/about/documents/>

¹⁷ <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

- Actively follow the development of AAI frameworks, and tune the EDCH AAI service to integrate best practices and usage models, such as IdP hinting.
- Assess the user experience during authentication, and improve the user interfaces.
- Provide users with reference documentation and a dedicated support channel not dependent on the AAI.
- Provide reference documentation to service providers, and ensure their integration with the AAI.

5.4.3.2 Suggested requirements for the EDCH AAI

In order to ensure the EDCH AAI is fit for purpose, a set of requirements were identified. The requirements are not definitive nor exhaustive, but serve as a framework to be adjusted to the EDCH:

1. Users must be able to use their organisational identity
2. Users from well-known identity federations from the Research and Education sector such as eduGAIN or the EOSC AAI, must be able to access the EDCH services
3. Users from OPERAS ID must be able to access the EDCH services
4. Users must be able to use identities from social media
5. Users must be able to link together their various identities
6. Users authenticated via the EDCH AAI must be able to access the OPERAS services
7. The EDCH AAI should meet the requirements of the EOSC AAI, allowing EDCH users to access EOSC services
8. The EDCH management team must be able to vet accounts and manage access to the different services. An initial layer of access control should apply to all services, while allowing individual services to manage any service-specific access rules
9. The AAI must inform services about the level of assurance of user identities, allowing them to make informed decisions regarding access authorisation
10. Service providers must be able to integrate with the AAI using SAML or OIDC authentication protocols
11. The AAI service must support the typical access use cases, such as access by a user with a browser, via a programmatic API, or as a service willing to interact with another EDCH service
12. The EDCH AAI must have a strong focus on information security and appropriately protect user data
13. The service must build on trustable and production-ready tools and services, and be able to meet the appropriate levels of availability and reliability

14. The AAI service must accommodate with available human and financial effort for EDCH funded development, maintenance and support
15. The service should be sustainable and an integral part of the EDCH funding and operational model.

5.4.3.3 Initial architecture of the EDCH AAI

Based on the AARC BPA framework (Figure 2), the following components that may be relevant to the EDCH AA are identified:

- **EDCH User identities**, representing categories of users that should be able to access the EDCH services via different identity providers.
- The **EDCH Services** to be accessed through the AAI. Additional third-party services (e.g. in the EOSC ecosystem) may also be accessed.
- A set of interoperable components that will associate user identities with EDCH services:
 - A **discovery service**, also called a WAYF (Where are you from), to allow users to select their desired identity provider
 - A **token translation service**, to ensure semantic interoperability of different protocols.
 - The **Identity Provider proxy** and the **Service Provider proxy**, (combinedly, **IdP/SP proxy**) to enable interconnection of identity providers with services.
 - **Documentation** for users, and processes to confirm consent for the **Acceptable Use Policy (AUP)** or **Privacy notices**.
- An **authorisation framework regulating** access to services, allowing to vet identities and control access based on user association with different groups and roles.

The list of components and their use will be refined during implementation. The goal is to build a flexible, tailored solution using solutions that support various integration scenarios.

5.4.3.4 Possible approaches for the EDCH AAI

A range of options is available—from custom-built solutions to established third-party providers—each with pros and cons. The choice must align with the specific needs of the EDCH.

If an internally managed service is qualified, solutions such as INDIGO IAM¹⁸, which is leveraging Keycloak¹⁹, or LemonLDAP::NG²⁰, possibly integrated with Fusion Directory²¹ as done in the context of the current OPERAS ID service²², could be used. As fully customised, this option would provide flexibility and ensure non-reliance on third party providers. However, it is demanding in terms of expertise and human resources required to develop, maintain and support the service.

At this stage, the EDCH may have limited capacity to develop and maintain an in-house AAI. While existing solutions can support deployment, the AAI must ensure high availability and trust, as any failure makes all dependent services inaccessible. Thus, a solution based on services provided by third parties will be assessed. The main advantage of this approach is the reallocation of operational costs to third parties (such as GÉANT's eduTEAMS²³ service, or EGI's Check-in²⁴ service). Such providers should offer clear service levels and have expert teams for development and operation. However, this shifts responsibility and creates dependency on third parties, potentially adding risks, limitations, and costs.

As a preliminary step for implementing the EDCH AAI, the main solutions supporting the federated access model will be identified, and assessed according to the EDCH requirements. Agreements will be made with any selected provider, covering important aspects such as the service operations, availability requirements, support, and the agreements on the funding and access model.

¹⁸ <https://indigo-iam.github.io/>

¹⁹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

²⁰ <https://lemonldap-ng.org/>

²¹ <https://www.fusiondirectory.org/>

²² <https://id.operas-eu.org/>

²³ <https://eduteams.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in/>

6. Conclusion

This report provided an overview of the EDCH, developed to support and coordinate the Diamond OA scholarly publishing initiatives in the ERA. Inspired by the recommendations of the Open Access Diamond Journals Study and the Action Plan for Diamond OA, the EDCH is currently being developed as a federated, community-driven infrastructure that addresses the fragmentation and sustainability faced by nonprofit OA publishers.

The EDCH aims to support a diverse range of stakeholders, including IPSPs, libraries, funders, RPOs, policymakers, learned societies, and research assessment agencies. It offers six core services: DOAS, Resources and Guidelines, Registry and Forum, Training Platform, Diamond Discovery Hub, and a suite of Publishing Tools.

The design of the EDCH was based on use cases identifying key user profiles, challenges, and service needs. These use cases helped design the services and the main components of the technical infrastructure; accordingly, they informed the operational scheme of the EDCH, which is structured around the converging activities of five Task Forces responsible for key operational areas: community-building, funding, skills development, quality assurance, and technical interoperability. The governance framework of the EDCH foresees three types of membership – Supporting, Operational, and Community Members— and is monitored by the Steering and Executive Committees.

The strategy for the long-term sustainability of the EDCH focuses on continuous stakeholder engagement, and the implementation of robust technical and organisational frameworks. Activities for community-building, service integration, and federated access infrastructure are already underway, aiming to integrate the EDCH with the Diamond OA landscape in the ERA.

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Annexes

1. Stakeholder types and roles

Stakeholder Type	Roles and activities
IPSP / IPTP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide services, infrastructure, and/ or technologies ● Manage publishing workflows ● Support editorial quality ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies, best practices, and standards
Learned Societies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publish in specific academic disciplines or professional fields ● Develop and maintain editorial standards, and disciplinary best practices ● Operate publishing platforms or collaborate with other IPSPs
Libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publish in specific academic disciplines ● Provide services, infrastructure, and/ or technologies ● Manage publishing workflows ● Support editorial quality ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies, best practices, and standards ● Coordinate infrastructure and publication at institutional and national levels
Research Performing Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies and best practices ● Publish in specific academic disciplines ● Manage services and infrastructure
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publish in specific academic disciplines ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies and best practices (as members of editorial boards) ● Support editorial quality (as members of editorial boards)

<p>Funders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fund research and publishing activities, at institutional, national, or international level ● Support publishing infrastructures ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies
<p>Policy makers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop and ensure compliance with policies
<p>Research Assessment Agencies</p>	<p>Evaluate the quality and impact of research Develop and apply criteria to support OA publishing models</p>

2. EDCH use case template

Title:	Stakeholder Category:	
Work package/Task:	4.1	
Document coordinator:		
Status:	[draft]	
Version:	[0.1]	
Open to commenting/feedback from all from/to		[]

Research team: [Author names]

References: [Links to documents used internally to support the drafting of use cases]

Stakeholder description: [Description of the scope and functions of the specific stakeholder type]

Key actors: types of institutions and agents relevant to the stakeholder profile

Roles / mission: Description of the stakeholder roles and activities within the institutional publishing ecosystem.

Summary: What the use cases have in common. Points to be addressed:

- What are the main challenges that the key actors face?
- What are their goals for using the portal?
- What are their expectations upon accessing the portal?
- What features would help meet these expectations?
- What services do they need from the portal?
- What resources (guidelines, documentation, training material) do they need from the portal?
- How often are they expected to use the portal?
- How likely are they to promote the portal in their communities and beyond?

Use case TEMPLATE [copy to add more use cases]

Title	
Key actor	
Roles/mission	
Context (a brief description of the use case)	
Challenges	
Type of information/guidance needed	
Types of resources needed	
Types of services needed	<p>[selection from the predefined list]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Documentation and guidance (best practices and standards / business models / policies) ● National/regional overviews ● Training and support ● Advocacy ● Knowledge exchange ● Networking
Suggested User workflow	
Relevant features/functionality	
Relevant components	
Success scenario	

3. EDCH Governance

European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)

Governance Structure

Membership Foundation

↑
SUPPORTED BY
↑

4. National Capacity Centres

Established National Capacity Centres	Country
Expertise Centre Diamond Open Access	Netherlands
Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)	Finland
Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología (FECYT)	Spain
Konzorcijum biblioteka Srbije za objedinjenu nabavku (KoBSON)	Serbia
National Documentation Centre (EKT)	Greece
Nordic Capacity Centre for Diamond Open Access	Nordic (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden)
Norwegian Network for Diamond Publishing	Norway
OpenEdition	France
Pub IN	Portugal
Servicestelle Diamond Open Access (SedOA)	Germany
Swedish Node for Diamond Open Access	Sweden

National Capacity Centres are being currently developed in the following countries: Croatia, the Czech Republic, Ireland, Italy, Poland, the United Kingdom, Slovenia and Switzerland.

